

UNITED STATES NAVY DIVING SAFETY PROGRAM

LCDR Raymond P. Swanson, USN

Supervisor of Diving
Commander Naval Sea Systems Command
Washington, D.C. 20362

Abstract

The United States Navy has an aggressive and comprehensive diving safety program. The program begins with the initial selection of candidates for formal diving training and follows the diver throughout training and into the Fleet in various forms. One of these forms is technical guidance with the primary vehicle being the United States Navy Diving Manual. This manual sets forth the procedures and equipment to be used for diving evolutions. A second form is the various inspections our diving systems, equipment and divers undergo. Included are INSURV, operational readiness, safety, administrative and systems/equipment certification inspections. A third form serves as an aid to assist the Navy to evaluate procedures and equipment. In this form computerized statistics are kept on all dives performed by Navy divers. This cradle-to-grave philosophy totally encompasses Navy diving and statistics show that it is successful.

Selection of Candidates

Candidates for initial diving training in the United States Navy are selected from qualified members after a careful screening process. The process can be separated into two phases. The first phase covers initial requirements and the second phase, the screening performed by a diving activity.

The first phase begins with identification of the volunteer from a specific source rating which is related to the type of work commonly performed by divers. Some examples of these source ratings are hull technicians, enginemen, boatswain mate and ordnance related ratings. Candidates must not be older than thirty years of age and must have a combined arithmetic and verbalization test score of 105; 110 if applying for the Explosive Ordnance Disposal program. Being within the age requirement increases the candidates' ability to satisfy the strenuous physical demands that will be encountered during initial training and by meeting the minimum test scores, the applicant should have the educational qualifications necessary to complete the academic portion of the training.

All candidates are required to pass a complete physical examination in accordance with the Manual of the Medical Department for duty involving diving. Candidates must also have good service records with no recent non-judicial punishments or court martials; the use of drugs within one year prior to application is disqualifying. Finally, prospective trainees must have anywhere between one to four years of obligated service (dependent upon the program requested) remaining on their enlistment or must be willing to obligate such time.

During the second phase, candidates are interviewed to determine motivation and suitability for the chosen diving program and also to ensure that they fully understand the type of training to be received and follow-on duty assignments. The interview is conducted by an activity qualified to perform operations or training in the candidates' chosen program. A Diving Officer or Master Diver conducts the interview for the diving programs. Either a Special Warfare Officer/Explosive Ordnance Disposal Officer or qualified enlisted Petty Officer First Class or above will conduct the interview for their respective programs.

After determining motivation and suitability, a physical fitness test is given to determine the candidates' physical ability to undergo training. This test is given in a timed sequence and includes running, swimming and exercises such as, but not limited to, pushups, situps and pullups. Upon successful completion of the physical fitness test, candidates receive a pressure and oxygen tolerance test at a hyperbaric recompression chamber. This test determines the candidate's ability to adapt to elevated atmospheric pressures and to breathe pure oxygen under pressure without adverse physiological reaction. This is important because in many circumstances Navy divers must breathe pure oxygen while under pressure in their normal working environment and also because pure oxygen is used in the Navy Treatment Tables for treatment of decompression sickness.

Selection of candidates is completed with a successful indoctrination dive using surface supplied deep sea gear. If not screened out earlier, the claustrophobic applicant will normally be discovered and screened out during

the indoctrination dive. Only Special Warfare and SCUBA diver applicants are omitted from the indoctrination dive because their particular mission requirements do not involve the use of deep sea diving equipment.

The careful and thorough selection for initial diving training significantly contributes to safety since it offers mature, highly motivated applicants which are both physically and psychologically fit for their forthcoming training. More advanced training will be available to these candidates after successfully completing their training and establishing a good performance record in a diving billet.

Diving Training

Selected candidates will report to one of several diving schools which train Divers Second Class. The curriculum at these schools is identical and is regularly monitored by the Chief of Naval Technical Training through the Navy Diving and Salvage Training Center in Panama City, Florida. Each instructor is an experienced Diver First Class, Master Diver or Diving Officer who is also a graduate of the Navy's Instructor School.

The diving student will undergo twelve weeks of training before becoming qualified as Diver Second Class. The training consists of diving physics, diving medicine, SCUBA, MK V (pronounced mark five) deep sea diving, MK 12 surface supplied diving, MK 1 and Jack Browne diving, underwater tools, underwater cutting and welding, equipment repair and hyperbaric chamber operation. During this training, safety is continuously stressed until it becomes infused into the student diver.

After gaining practical diving experience with the fleet, some of the more qualified divers will be sent to the Naval Diving and Salvage Training Center for seventeen more weeks of training as Diver First Class. The course begins with a review of diving physics, diving medicine and MK 12 surface supplied diving and progresses into advanced techniques of underwater cutting and welding. They receive underwater demolition training, salvage, helium-oxygen mixed gas diving, splitting and mixing of helium-oxygen, submarine rescue chamber operation and system certification procedures. This course of instruction prepares the diver with the knowledge to supervise diving operations. Upon return to the fleet, the diver will be constantly evaluated for the qualities of leadership, knowledge and maturity necessary to be a diving supervisor. When deemed appropriate, the command will qualify deserving divers as "diving supervisor".

Completion of a minimum of two years as a Diver First Class enables recommended divers to attend a seventeen week course for saturation diving. During this course divers receive both saturation diving theory and practical saturation diving training. At this point, highly

qualified and experienced Divers First Class or Saturation Divers may be recommended as candidates for Master Diver/Master Saturation Diver evaluation. These divers receive three weeks advanced training in diving physics, diving medicine and system certification. They undergo an intensive two week period of diving operations where their knowledge of diving and ability to react accurately to stressful situations is evaluated. Only the best and most qualified divers the fleet has to offer earn the title of "Master Diver".

During each successive phase of the individual diver's training, knowledge of physics, medicine, equipment and procedures is increased. This knowledge is the building block of safety. As each diver progresses through the various classes of diver, he better understands and becomes increasingly aware of the hazards of his chosen profession. In this way, the diver is an integral part of the Navy diving safety program.

Guidance

When a diver leaves one of the Diving School Commands for an operational tour of duty, he becomes physically separated from a key source of up-to-date information that can affect his performance as a diver. Since it is important that all divers be kept abreast of the latest information in their field if they are to dive safely and efficiently, directives are issued. These directives announce official changes in policy, procedures and techniques or any combination of them.

Perhaps the most important of these instructions is the United States Navy Diving Manual. This manual provides the most current source of information in the field of Navy diving. It has a threefold purpose. First, to assemble all pertinent available technical information necessary for the diver to perform underwater tasks; second, to provide a vehicle for the dissemination of new information and; third, to authorize the use of specific practices for Navy divers performing underwater tasks.

The United States Navy Diving Manual covers both air and mixed-gas helium-oxygen diving from SCUBA through surface-supplied to saturation diving. It sets forth the safe operational and depth limits of each type of equipment and provides guidance for emergencies. The Manual also provides decompression tables to be used in all types of United States Navy diving and in the event of decompression sickness, it provides the treatment tables to be utilized.

Messages and directives are issued when, in the case of messages, rapid dissemination of information is required or when addressing policy matters or less technical procedures and practices than those in the United States Navy Diving Manual. The use of the Diving Manual, messages and directives assures timely receipt of information and a uniform application of safe procedures and practices throughout the Navy.

Inspections

Careful selection of candidates, thorough training of divers and timely dissemination of directives supports the personnel portion of the safety program. However, if the equipment or system is unsafe, all the time and effort spent in developing the diver has been wasted. The next integral step in the overall safety program addresses the material aspect of diving equipment and systems.

Systems certification pertains to all manned diving systems and includes the design, material, fabrication or construction process, quality assurance, testing, operability and maintenance of these systems. It begins with an applicant submitting a request for certification of a proposed diving system. The request outlines the system operational characteristics such as depth, time limits and breathing media supply. The procedure for certification will require the requesting activity to be able to document and prove that qualified personnel have performed all work in accordance with established and approved procedures. A certificate of certification will be issued on-site verification of the above by the System Certification Authority and the performance of a demonstration dive.

Certification is given for a specific period of time after which the system must be reinspected. During the interval of initial certification and reinspection, all work performed on the system that penetrates defined boundaries which are considered life critical must be thoroughly documented. Once again, only authorized procedures and qualified personnel can be used to perform required repairs. All routine maintenance and its periodicity is prescribed in a preventive maintenance schedule much the same as that of an automobile.

Although the Certification Program is one of the most comprehensive material inspections, it is not the only inspection that diving systems or for that matter divers must undergo. Approximately every three years an INSURV (Inspection and Survey) Inspection is conducted by the Naval Sea Systems Command Board of Inspection and Survey. The inspection team evaluates the whole ship including the diving system. Machinery and equipment is examined to determine its condition. Administrative, operating and emergency procedures are also reviewed. Results from this detailed inspection are used to plan ship and system overhauls and to point out safety and procedural deficiencies.

Another inspection, the Operational Readiness Inspection, is conducted annually by the type commander to determine a ship or units ability to perform its assigned mission. This inspection examines the amalgamation of the diver, the equipment and the procedures into an effective working unit. During the Operational Readiness Inspection, diving units will be

required to conduct full scale diving and associated evolutionary operations.

The last inspections conducted are the Safety and Administrative Inspections. The Safety Inspection is conducted through mutual agreement between the command and the Naval Safety Center. All aspects of safety are examined and recommendations are made for improvements that will further enhance the safety of the unit and its personnel. The final inspection covers the paperwork or administrative procedures of each command. Medical records, diving logs and diving instructions, to name a few, are checked to see that they are current and to ascertain that proper administrative procedures are being utilized.

Each of these inspections further infuses the safety philosophy of the diving program into not only the diver but also those closely associated with the diver's mission. An additional benefit not often recognized is that each inspection is conducted by a different level of command and by different activities and individuals. In this way subtle influences are precluded from affecting inspection results.

Record Keeping

All divers are required to maintain a personal diving log and to submit a record of each dive to the Naval Safety Center through their diving supervisors and diving officers. The individual diving log provides each diver with a personal record of his dives while promoting a degree of personal pride and esprit de corps. The Diving Log form which is sent to the Naval Safety Center (commonly referred to as "9940") provides data for analysis. It is the data which is of most interest to the safety program.

The 9940 form sent to the Naval Safety Center is screened by computer. Analysis of the data provides such statistics as the number of dives performed over any period by equipment and type of diver. These statistics are routinely provided to the fleet on a semi-annual basis. By varying the output format, potential problems with decompression tables, equipment, etc. can be identified and more thoroughly evaluated. Since the form also covers injuries and deaths resulting from diving, it provides critical information to medical personnel which may be helpful in establishing new treatment techniques.

Conclusion

The United States Navy's multipronged approach to diving safety encompasses the Navy divers, their supervisors, and the equipment and procedures used in the performance of their underwater tasks. The diver is not forgotten once he graduates from school. Advanced education is provided for those qualified, criteria

is set for the development of new systems and a system of checks and balances is maintained for both the diver and the equipment during operational tours. Although it took many years to get to this point, it was well worth the effort. During the ten year period from January 1970 through December 1979, United States Navy divers conducted over 613,000 dives while incurring only six fatalities. This equates to 0.0009 percent or nine ten-thousands of a percent. In examining U.S. Underwater Diving Fatality Statistics, 1970-79 issued by the National Underwater Accident Data Center, there were one hundred twenty-three known fatalities among occupational divers over that same period. Although the number of dives performed by civilian occupational divers during that period is unknown, the Navy's record remains impressive and shows that the diving safety program is effective.